

BUILT 04

Age-friendly services

Services which we need in our neighbourhoods for our healthy ageing.

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Warsaw University
of Technology

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BUILT

MODULE 4

Age-friendly services

In this module, you will learn about age-friendly services, which are an indispensable component of an age-friendly neighbourhood. Their availability and accessibility highly impact the quality of life of all residents, particularly the older ones.

Introduction

Age-friendly neighbourhoods in urban and rural areas are necessary to keep older adults healthy and active. One of the basic components of age-friendly neighbourhoods is a thriving business sector. Small local businesses are directly connected with older people. They are more than just commercial activities; they help older adults reduce isolation and loneliness. Going shopping and using other amenities like a hairdresser or cafeteria gives the older person the opportunity to meet and talk with others. Often, shopkeepers or service providers become important figures in a local community as they lend a friendly ear to older customers' needs and problems.

Why services should be age-friendly?

The number of older adults has been growing continuously and is expected to grow substantially in the future.

Despite this fact, many people feel that businesses do not see older people as customers and do not respond to their needs.

As a service provider, making your business age-friendly may have a positive influence on your bottom line due to:

- increased number of customers
- better reception as a customer-friendly service
- more loyal customers as older persons tend to get attached

If a service is age-friendly, it is not only suitable for older adults but also many others, including:

- pregnant women,
- parents with children in strollers,
- people with sight, hearing or mobility limitations,
- people with limited communication skills (E.g. foreigners not knowing your national language) and
- people with a mental illness.

In the end, age-friendly services are good for all customers.

Did you know?

The Silver Economy is a new economy sector which emerged as a response to the needs of the growing population group: older adults.

The European Silver Economy is expected to expand by approximately 5% per year and contribute over 5.7 trillion € by 2025 to Europe's economy.

The purpose of the module

This module is designed to provide insight into age-friendly services. The availability of such services at the local, neighbourhood level supports older people to remain independent and healthy for longer. It also contributes to higher social integration.

The purpose of the module is to show practical, no-cost or low-cost tips to make your business more age-friendly.

The module is divided into three chapters. First, you will learn about the services particularly needed by older adults. Then, the focus will be laid on their features. Finally, you will get some tips on how to attract older customers.

What will you learn in this module

- 1 The types of age-friendly services.
- 2 The features of age-friendly services.
- 3 How to attract the clients.

Chapters in this module

1

Age-friendly services: types

2

Age-friendly services: features

3

How to attract older customers

 BUILT **MODULE 4** **CHAPTER 1**

Age-friendly services: types

In this chapter, you will learn about the different types of services an older adult, but not only, may need.

In the currently fast-changing times, the necessity of making user-provider distance as small as possible became vital.

What will you learn in this chapter

1 Neighbourhood and proximity services.

2 The power of craftsmanship.

3 Types of services older adults need.

Introduction

In this chapter, you will learn about different types of services, particularly needed by older adults on a neighbourhood level. Meeting life's needs in the immediate vicinity increases the quality of life and helps older adults to stay healthy and independent for longer. Undoubtedly, it also has a positive impact on the development of local entrepreneurship and commerce.

The importance of direct access to basic services has increased significantly during the pandemic period.

Neighbourhood and proximity services

A neighbourhood is a part of a town where people live. A town, suburban area or city can be composed of many different neighbourhoods.

The house and neighbourhood where one lives highly impact the health and quality of one's life. A good neighbourhood is a safe, friendly space where people know one another and are ready to lend a hand. This strong sense of community is particularly important for vulnerable groups such as kids, women and seniors.

Neighbourhoods should be compact and pedestrian friendly. They should be equipped with basic services like groceries or bakeries located within about five minutes of walking from one's home. This makes a quarter of a mile or 400 metres.

This means that in a good neighbourhood, everyone should have access to the services needed daily within five minutes of walking from their home.

Providing basic services on a neighbourhood level may positively influence community building. A neighbourhood with proximity services and a strong community is a great place for everyone to live.

Food provision

The ability to buy essential food products by oneself at an older age helps in remaining independent and healthy. Even shopping for two small rolls may be an excellent opportunity to socialise. Easier access to healthy food is also an important feature of a good neighbourhood.

Food market

Older adults value good quality food products from local providers. They greatly enjoy local food markets.

Relevant assortment

Small, local shops can better adjust their products offer to the older adults' needs. Moreover, shopping more often and in smaller quantities can save money because less food will go to waste.

Location

A grocery or service with direct customer contact should be located in an area highly frequented by pedestrians.

Local grocery

Larger shops are often very crowded and loud. It is easy to get lost in such a space. Moreover, self-service checkouts are sometimes tricky to use for older adults who prefer more direct contact with the seller. The seniors like very much small groceries located in the immediate vicinity. The shopkeeper often knows his or her clients' names and what they usually buy. He or she can also adjust his offer to the customers' needs.

Indeed, shopping may be a vital way of alleviating loneliness which is considered to be a major cause of depression.

Shop on wheels

The availability of food provision in some rural areas may be low, causing some seniors living in these areas to have difficulties buying food products.

In such a case, a great solution seems to be a shop on wheels which can reach every location. In many countries, franchise brands with shops on wheels are present. If you know that in your region there are neighbourhoods where a shop on wheels would be needed, maybe such a business idea is good to consider.

Places to eat and meet

It is true that the more often people eat with others, the more they feel happy and satisfied with their lives. In the past, mealtimes were events when the whole settlement or village came together. This is how a strong community was built. Similarly today the possibility of eating together is important not only for us as individuals but also as a community.

To socialise

It does not have to be a big meal, it can be just a cup of coffee or tea with a snack.

To celebrate

There are some moments in life which require a special celebration. Dinner in a restaurant might be a good option.

To eat affordably

Local canteens, milk bars and bistros are places where you can eat inexpensively and, more importantly, also healthily, unlike in fast food chains.

Beauty and wellness

Everyone has the right to care for one's appearance; it is not restricted by gender or age. Local hairdressers, nail studios and beauty parlours are also needed in neighbourhoods with an ageing population. Besides, getting a haircut is a basic need not a luxury.

Visiting such venues is also an excellent opportunity to meet and talk with others.

Did you know?

That a barber is one of the oldest professions? Until recently, a barber has been considered almost an extinct profession.

Nowadays, it is experiencing a renaissance as a result of a lumberjack-style fashion.

The power of craftsmanship

Industrial mass production caused us to almost forget about handmade products that are tailored to one's specific needs. With the ongoing ageing population process resulting in a greater diversity of needs, the production of goods by craftsmen should become more accessible.

Older adults value high quality and direct service. They can be dedicated customers of local craftsmen.

Craftsmanship is also good for the environment as it makes less waste and utilises less energy than a typical industrial production.

Food craftsmanship

Food quality is essential to keep us in good health. Unfortunately, many food products offered in large retail stores are produced industrially. They are full of chemicals and made of poor quality components. Even though they may taste good, they are detrimental to our health.

Baker

Bread is one of the basic products we like to consume on daily basis. Local bakeries offering tasty and healthy bread will be very much appreciated particularly by older adults.

Confectioner

It is also nice to have a good confectioner in the vicinity. As the number of diabetics grows, the demand for sugar-free cakes will appear and this requires some skills.

Butcher

We should generally cut down on meat consumption. If we decide to eat meat, we should have access to good quality one which a local butcher can provide.

Clothes, shoes and accessories craftsmanship

Older people are often very attached to their belongings and would rather fix them than throw them away. Unfortunately, many neighbourhoods lack craftsmen who can do this.

Tailor

Instead of buying new clothes, many older adults would rather remake the old ones or make new ones by a tailor.

Shoemaker

Shoemaker is a disappearing profession nowadays. A local shoemaker is important for older adults as he can repair the old shoes but also adjust the new ones to specific feet needs.

Leatherworker

A torn ear from your favourite leather handbag or a belt where holes need to be added? This is what the leatherworker deals with.

Accessories and crafts

Older people are very attached to things with which memories are associated, such as jewellery or watches. The possibility of getting them repaired if needed would be very welcomed in an age-friendly neighbourhood.

Jeweller

A ring that has become too tight or a broken chain? This is something your local jeweller can take care of.

Watchmaker

Although traditional watches are not as popular nowadays as before, some specialists able to repair them will be needed.

Optician

A local optician is also very much needed in a neighbourhood as not only older adults but also younger people need to wear glasses nowadays.

Prevalence of women

Women tend to live longer than men. It is often said that old age is characterised by feminisation. This fact is worth considering when thinking about services needed in your neighbourhood.

Repairs

Older adults, but not only, are often unable to carry out repairs on a variety of household items. It would be great if a person had access to these services within 15 minutes of walking.

Bike repair

Riding a bike is recommended for almost everyone and is becoming increasingly popular. Therefore, local bike services are needed.

Home appliance repair

Repairing home appliance instead of throwing it away is sometimes possible. It is essential to have someone who can do this in the neighbourhood.

Electronic device repair

This is a fairly new service, and the demand is growing continuously.

Home caretakers

A personal custodian service who can fix the light or can take care of the garden is very welcomed by the older adults, particularly those with some health issues.

Locksmith and plumber

Demand for these services is particularly prevalent in old buildings, which often are inhabited by older adults.

Upholsterer

Older adults are also bound to their furniture. Sometimes it is enough to change upholstery fabric, and the furniture will be again aesthetic and useful.

Furniture carpenter

Restoration of old furniture is becoming more and more popular not only among older adults.

Cleaning services

Last but not least the cleaning services are crucial in an ageing neighbourhood. It is not just about domestic cleaning services but also about washing and hanging curtains, and cleaning upholstery or windows.

Activity 1

Take a walk around your neighbourhood. Try to observe what services exist. Are there any missing?

Think about those which would be needed.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUILT | **MODULE 4** | **CHAPTER 1** Age-friendly services: types

What services are needed in an age-friendly neighbourhood?

- A night club
- A large shopping mall
- A grocery
- A bicycle service
- A factory
- A bakery

Chapter summary

1

You have learnt what neighbourhoods and proximity services are.

2

You have learnt about the growing importance of craftsmanship in tailoring a product to one's specific needs.

3

You have learnt about different services older adults may particularly need.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You know what neighbourhood and proximity services are.

2

You know what services might be needed.

3

You have learned about the power of craftsmanship and how you could use it.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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BUILT

MODULE 4

CHAPTER 2

Age-friendly services: features

In this chapter, you will learn about the features of age-friendly services. Remember that making your service more age-friendly is not only good for your customers in older age but also for others.

What will you learn in this chapter

1 Features of age-friendly services responding to typical limitations of older adults.

2 About Universal Design.

Age-friendly

Most older people are healthy, independent individuals. However, with age, some changes may occur, and they can get some physical restrictions. It is estimated that:

- 1/3 of older adults have hearing problems
- 2/3 of them need to wear glasses
- many of them have some mobility issues with different intensities (which may also depend on weather and other circumstances)

Fortunately, most changes in your business venue can be easily introduced so that it can become age-friendly.

Dementia-friendly

It is estimated that even one-third of us will get dementia in older age. The longer we live, the more probable getting dementia becomes. You can learn more about dementia in the **Healthy 05 Cognitive impairment and Dementia** and **Built 03 Dementia-friendly home** modules.

Going shopping is one of the favourite activities of older people and those affected by dementia. Therefore, these venues should be adapted to their needs to enable them to remain active and independent for longer.

HEALTHY

BUILT

Introduction

In this chapter, we will focus on the features of age-friendly services which respond to the typical limitations linked with:

- Mobility
- Sight
- Hearing

We will also refer to dementia as well as visual and sound communication. Finally, Universal Design as the recommended approach of designing spaces, products and services will be presented.

Mobility

Remember that if you make your service or product available only for the young, you exclude the old. However, if you make it available to the old, you will include everyone and extend your customers' range.

Easily opening doors

Heavy doors can pose a real barrier. Pay attention that they are easy to open. If it is particularly heavy and difficult to move, you may consider installing an electric door drive.

Chair with armrest

Older adults, if having some mobility impairments, may need support on armrests when sitting or standing up.

The chairs or sitting places should not be too low or too soft.

Anti slippery floor

The floor should be slip-resistant even when wet.

Mobility

It is true that making a venue fully accessible to e.g. a wheelchair user can be unrealistic due to financial limitations or simply limited space.

However, there are other smaller and less costly measures which you can introduce to increase the safety of your customers.

Think about:

- the entrance: are there stairs? Is it possible to make fewer of them?
- are the pathways uncluttered and allow for moving with a walker?

Mobility: counter and shelves

Pay attention to the counter level, which should be available to wheelchair users. The recommended height is 90cm.

Many older adults have mobility problems with their arms. That's why try to avoid shelves higher than 150 cm level.

Sight

For vision-impaired persons, good lighting is essential. As you know from the **Built 02 Age-friendly home**, older adults need more light than younger people. They require three times the light to see as younger people. The venue should be evenly lit, avoiding building up shadows or dark corners. Lightening and surfaces should not produce glare as older adults are very sensitive to it.

Large windows and natural lighting are welcomed, but if overheating becomes a problem, install some shadings.

BUILT

Sight

Many shops, including the local ones, introduce magnifying glasses to help their customers read descriptions of foodstuffs in small print.

Such a magnifying glass can be fixed on a food shelf.

Visual communication

Visual communication uses visual elements to communicate information or ideas. It is very important for older adults and those with cognitive impairments. It should be easily recognisable and well visible.

Well visible exterior signage

Ensure you have a good sign for your business that is easy to see and read. Check if local regulations referring to signs and banners exists.

Recognizable washroom signs

Sometimes a verbal description is not necessary and graphics are sufficient. Make sure they are understandable.

Product descriptions

When you use some text, ensure that the font is large enough, is simple in shape, and there is sufficient contrast between the font and background.

Visual communication and dementia

Well-recognizable signage at the eye level is particularly important for people with dementia, who can get lost or disorientated easily.

Not only should toilets have clear signs but also check out, exit and other essential elements of the venue.

People with dementia can be confused by patterns on the floor, shiny elements and mats or rugs which have a different colour than the rest of the floor (they can perceive it as a hole and be frightened of it). Try to put a mat in the entrance area in a similar colour to the rest of the floor.

Hearing

Older adults but also people with autism prefer to be in quiet places. Noisy spaces make them feel uncomfortable and sometimes even irritated.

If there is much noise in your venue, you may consider installing some acoustics panels on walls or ceilings. Also, upholstered furniture hung tapestries, and curtains can positively impact acoustic comfort in your venue.

A quiet area can be made in a restaurant (by means of i.e. partition walls) where tables could be dedicated mainly to older customers.

Sound communication

Sound is important because it informs us and moves us in a way visuals cannot. It also impacts the way we perceive a given space and whether we feel good in it.

Adequate volume and pleasant

The sound should not be too loud and dynamic. This not only refers to the music but also sounds produced by restaurant pagers which are sometimes shrill.

Quiet hours

Depending on your customers' needs, you may want to introduce quiet hours, which could be appreciated by some older adults, people with autism and people with dementia.

Music for all

If you want to put some music in your venue, think of the one that would match the tastes of the young and old.

Do the task!

Do you remember Nikos? He runs a small, local shop with daily products for his customers. He knows them very well and he feels attached to them as well. They are mostly older people and Nikos noticed that some of them began to have problems with walking, hearing, or seeing. He is really concerned about it and he would like to make his shop more age-friendly.

- ✓ Meet and get to know Nikos. You can find more about him [here](#).
- ✓ Can you give him some tips on improving mobility?
- ✓ Can you give him some tips on visuals?
- ✓ Can you give him some tips on sounds and acoustics?

Universal Design

If you want to make your service or product age-friendly, you should be aware of Universal Design and its principles.

The term Universal Design was coined and popularised by architect Ronald Mace in the 1990s. However, the very idea of treating people with disabilities as equal participants in society is earlier. It was gradually developed over the course of the 20th Century when people were living longer than ever before, and the average life expectancy of people with severe impairments was increasing.

Moreover, a large number of war veterans with disabilities made governments introduce equal rights and anti-discrimination legislation.

Universal Design is the design and composition of an environment so that it can be accessed, understood and used to the greatest extent possible by all people, regardless of their age, size, ability or disability.

Universal Design is not a one size fits all approach. In fact, it concentrates on the needs of users with diverse disabilities and characteristics. But, the resulting design is accessible to, usable by and appealing to all users, including those without any impairments.

Consequently, a universally designed product, service or environment becomes available to a higher number and a wider range of potential customers.

Did you know?

The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities was adopted on 13 December 2006 by the United Nations. The Convention includes the definition of Universal Design.

The convention has already been ratified by 185 countries worldwide. Also, the European Union has signed it.

The concept of Universal Design is being introduced into the legislation of the signatory countries.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUILT | **MODULE 4** | **CHAPTER 2** Age-friendly services features

If you design a product or a service for older adults following a Universal Design approach, then it will be available to a higher number and a wider range of potential customers.

- True
- False

Chapter summary

1

You have learnt about the features of an age-friendly service related to mobility impairment.

2

You have learnt about the features of an age-friendly service related to sight impairment.

3

You have learnt about the features of an age-friendly service related to hearing impairment.

4

You have learnt about Universal Design.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You know the basic features of an age-friendly service.

2

You know what to do to make your venue more age-friendly.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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BUILT

MODULE 4

CHAPTER 3

Attracting customers

In this chapter, you will get tips on attracting customers to your age-friendly service. We will focus on the older customers who may need different approaches than the younger ones.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 What can be done on a neighbourhood level to attract older customers.
- 2 What can be done specifically in a venue to attract older customers.

Introduction

Probably the best marketing for the age-friendly service is word-of-mouth marketing. People talk to each other, and they share their experiences they got with a given service.

In this chapter, we will look at what can be done at the neighbourhood level to make the services more accessible to seniors and people with dementia. Then, we will focus on some tips an individual shopkeeper or service provider may introduce.

Location, location and location

It is commonly stated that the success of a shop or any service venue is determined by three factors: location, location and location.

If a street or a town square is highly frequented by pedestrians, the facilities located along them will have many customers. Such streets and squares are the focal points of the neighbourhood. They serve not only as providing shopping opportunities but also as meeting spaces for the inhabitants.

When choosing a location for your business venue, pay attention to its accessibility in terms of architectural design (e.g. entrance without stairs) but also in terms of urban design, whether this location is reached by many people.

As you already know, allowing people with dementia to shop independently is vital to keep them healthy and support their carers.

As indicated in the module **General 01 SHAFE and me**, dementia-friendly walkable shopping routes are being created across the Netherlands. In Rotterdam, two routes marked with yellow and green can be followed. These routes form two separate loops where persons with dementia can walk around. They are a part of the main street, where main amenities are located. Each loop includes adjacent building blocks where housing is located. In this way, the inhabitants with dementia can easily access the route. They do not get lost and can comfortably reach the shop and return safely.

GENERAL

How about painting a dementia-friendly shopping route in your neighbourhood?

Can you remember what fun it was to draw with chalk on the pavement as a child?

Painting the shopping route on the pavement with your neighbours and colleagues can be fun as well. It can have a form of a line or flowers like in a great project by Sanne Janssen and Gerjanne van Gink: <https://vergeetmijnietpad.nl/>.

Before you start, inform local authorities about the idea. They might be interested in raising awareness of dementia and might be willing to support it. Also, other retailers and service providers from the neighbourhood might be willing to participate.

Tips on the dementia friendly walking route creation

If you have gathered some parties willing to participate in creating the dementia-friendly shopping route, you should consider:

- **The date**

An excellent opportunity to create such a route is the International Alzheimer's Day on 21 September. The local authorities might be more interested in joining the initiative if the date is meaningful.

- **Designing the route carefully**

Remember that it should have a loop shape and not be too long. The walking time should be around 15 minutes, which makes 1.2 km. Include in the route places important for seniors: shops, a pharmacy, but also a park, a church etc.

- **Ideas of others**

Ideally, the route would be designed during a workshop with interested parties. However, this is not always possible. Therefore, you can conduct an online consultation by posting the idea and design proposal on social media.

- **Using washable paint**

It is the simplest and also the cheapest solution. It may also act as part of the route design consultation process. The users may want to change the course of the route. In this way, the final route will better suit the users' needs.

A pin-up board

A pin-up board can be hung in a local retail centre or a grocery store. The customers may place their announcements there or find ads referring to their needs (like cleaning services).

Some local events can be advertised in this way.

The pin-up boards still have a wide reach. Especially among older adults, they remain an important means of communication about local activities and events.

Food shopping

Making food shopping accessible to older people, and particularly people with dementia, is increasingly important. Research shows that for older people staying in control of their food shopping is key to retaining independence and a sense of belonging to a community. Moreover, it is also reported that many seniors are at risk of malnutrition.

Apart from making the venue more accessible in physical terms, as presented in the previous chapter, some other measures can be taken to improve food shopping by older adults.

Recipes in a grocery store

The shopkeeper may encourage his customers to prepare meals reflecting the season and available fruit and vegetables.

He can put a chosen recipe (in large print) on a visible place and also make smaller copies to be taken home.

This can inspire customers to try recipes they perhaps never tried before. The recipes could be changed every week or two, depending on the availability of the products.

Do you remember the Portuguese pumpkin cake recipe from the module **HEALTHY 02 Lifestyle and Therapy**?

This could be a good start!

HEALTHY

Did you know?

Urinary incontinence is a common and distressing complaint by many older adults. Many of them resign from walking outside because of it.

You can make toilet use available to older people in your venue. In many countries, such venues are given appropriate designations. Their experience has been very positive as the number of customers has increased significantly.

A place to seat

Apart from the lack of toilets, another barrier discouraging older adults from walking outside is the insufficient seating places.

If you are a shopkeeper or a service provider, try to put a chair in your venue where a tired person could sit and rest for a while.

The experience shows that venues offering a chair also increased their revenues, and they were perceived as very customer-friendly.

Restaurants and canteens

An age-friendly restaurant or canteen should have low-fat, heart-smart, low-sodium meals on the menu. Also, smaller portions offered at lower prices are worth considering.

Plates should contrast with the table surface and minimise the risk of burns. They should also be shaped to help you pick up the food yourself with a spoon or fork (higher rands). Special, heavier cutlery dedicated to persons affected by Parkinson's disease is also worth considering. Such persons often find it embarrassing to eat with trembling hands in public.

Get feedback

You can ask your customers to share with you their opinion on your service. For example, you could place a feedback box with small pieces of paper at the entrance of the shop/restaurant. You may also take a look at the opinions posted on the Internet and social media.

Vintage design

Older adults feel good in an environment they know well. No necessarily ultra-modern and fashionable design is needed for an age-friendly service venue. Older adults, particularly those with some memory loss, can enjoy spaces that resemble, to some extent, those they recall from their youth.

The shape of font, interior design or details (like posters) can relate to the 1960s or 1970s, the years of the youth of today's seniors.

Surprisingly, this style is also very appealing to the young nowadays.

Communication

The way an older adult is approached by the service provider is vital. Staff should speak clearly while looking directly at a person. There should also be paper and pen at the service counter to provide options for communication. The staff should also know how to assist customers with vision or hearing impairments.

Learn more about communication, including plain language, in the module **General 02 Communication**.

GENERAL

Communication and dementia

People affected by dementia are often isolated from the community due to a lack of understanding. They can leave the shop without paying because they forget to pay. They can be treated as thefts which is very painful for them and their carers. Sometimes, too much noise may cause them to become anxious. It is important that you learn about dementia (See the module **Healthy 05 Cognitive impairment and Dementia**) to know how to approach your customers affected by this illness.

HEALTHY

Get marked!

If your service is age-friendly and you are constantly working to be even more age-friendly, let your customers know about it. Put a sign or notice showing that your service meets the older customers' needs.

In Poland, the company „Ok Senior” offers audits and certification schemes for products and services dedicated to older adults. Shops, service providers, sports centres and many other premises can be signed with the OK Senior badge if they meet the necessary requirements.

For more information, visit: www.oksenior.pl.

Chapter summary

1

You have learnt about the importance of the location of your business venue and dementia-friendly shopping route.

2

You have learnt that food shopping is essential for older adults.

3

You have learnt that making toilets and seating places more available encourages older adults to walk out. Services offering a seat and making toilet use available increase their profits.

4

You have learned that communication with older customers is essential and that learning about cognitive impairments is necessary.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUILT | **MODULE 4** | **CHAPTER 3** | Attracting customers

Age-friendly services and shops are not needed in the local neighbourhoods.

True

False

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You know that older customers need some specific approaches, which can be appreciated by the younger customers.

2

You know that you can take some actions on a neighbourhood level to make services more age and dementia-friendly.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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Module summary

1

You have learnt about different services older adults may need in their neighbourhoods.

2

You have learnt about the features of age-friendly services responding to typical limitations of older adults.

3

You have learnt that shopping is one of the favourite activities of older adults and the shops should be adjusted to their needs.

4

You have learnt how to attract older customers to your service venue and that older adults are very fond of craftsmanship.

Module completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this module!

Summary of acquired skills

- 1 You know what an age-friendly service is.

- 2 You know how to create one.

- 3 You know how important age-friendly services are for the seniors.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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